

References

1. <https://ansp.md/situatia-epidemiologica-prin-infectia-cu-hiv-masurile-de-control-si-raspuns-anul-2021/>
2. Vladislav GOGU , Mircea BEȚIU , Lucia PÂRȚĂNĂ , Angela NAGĂȚ , Svetlana POPOVICI , Irina CUCEROVA , Tatiana CAIȘÎM , Anna IASINCOVSCAIA , Vasile ȚĂBĂRNĂ. Manifestările cutaneo-mucoase în infecția HIV/SIDA. În: Curierul medical, Iunie 2016, Vol. 59, No 3. <http://hdl.handle.net/20.500.12710/2967>
3. Holban, T., Plăcină, Gh., Cojocaru, S., Iarvoi, L., Cebătorescu, V. Ghid practic Infecția cu HIV: ETIOLOGIE, PATOGENIE, TABLOU CLINIC, DIAGNOSTIC, TRATAMENT, Chișinău 2011 <https://library.usmf.md/sites/default/files/2020-10/Infec-tia%20cu%20HIV%20Etiologie%20Patologie%20Tablou%20clinic%20Diagnostic%20Tratament%202011.pdf>
4. Bețiu M., Dermatovenerologie. Manual pentru studenți. Chișinău 2013, 425p. <https://dermatovenerologie.usmf.md/sites/default/files/inline-files/Dermatovenerologie%20manual.pdf>
5. Cedeno-Laurent F., Gomez-Flores M., Mendez N., Ancer-Rodriguez J., Bryant J., Gaspari A., Trujillo J.. New insights into HIV-1-primary skin disorders. Journal of the International AIDS Society. 2011. Volume 14, Issue 1. p.1-17. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1758-2652-14-5>
6. Sanín AM, Londoño Ángela M, Gil V, Mejía AM, Aguirre HD, Vásquez EM, Valencia C, Cardona C. Manifestaciones mucocutáneas y su relación con el recuento de linfocitos T CD4 en pacientes infectados con el virus de inmunodeficiencia humana hospitalizados en Medellín, Colombia. Biomédica 2022;42:278-89. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.7705/biomedica.6117>

UPDATES IN ETIOPATHOGENESIS, CYTOLOGICAL AND IMMUNOCYTOCHEMICAL DIAGNOSIS IN LOW-GRADE SQUAMOUS INTRAEPITHELIAL LESIONS OF THE CERVIX (LSIL)

Capatina Elena,

*Student, Faculty of General Medicine,
State University of Medicine and Pharmacy
„Nicolae Testemitanu”
Republic of Moldova, Chisinau*

Tudor Rotaru

*Associate Professor, Department of Oncology,
State University of Medicine and Pharmacy
„Nicolae Testemitanu”
Republic of Moldova, Chisinau*

Abstract

Introduction:

Low-grade squamous intraepithelial lesions (LSIL) is the primary underlying modification of the development of cervical cancer, and the most important etiological factor is the human papillomavirus. In the Republic of Moldova this diagnosis tends to progress due to an insufficiently developed screening programme.

Materials and methods: retrospective and prospective data including medical records of 135 patients admitted to the Oncology Institute of the Republic of Moldova during the period 2017-2021 in which those patients diagnosed with LSIL were detected and studied.

Results: Of the 135 patients studied, the prevalence of ASC-US in patients aged 17-26 years was about 18.75%. About 49.63% detected with high-risk HPV types 16, 18, 31, 33, 35, 39, 45, 51, 52, 56, 59, 66, 68. The method most chosen by patients in the diagnostic process was the ThinPrepPap test, about 49% of patients.

Conclusions: The incidence of cervical cancer is increasing in developing countries where cervical screening programmes are not yet well organized. The human papillomavirus (HPV) has an affinity for epithelial tissue, especially at sites with lesions, and infection itself depends on changes in the basal layer of the epithelium.

Keywords: LSIL, HPV, cervix.

Introduction

Cervical cancer is one of the most common diseases detected in women with a global distribution, ranking second among malignant neoplasms of the cervix, second only to breast cancer [5]. The condition of development of the malignant process at the level of the cervix, is represented by precancerous changes induced by the infection with human papillomavirus (HPV), generating low-grade intraepithelial lesions (LSIL). However, not all women infected with HPV develop

cervical cancer, as it depends on the immune system of the infected body and the type of HPV genotype.

The papillomavirus genome possesses three regions [7] the short, circular HPV genome encoded by 8 proteins (E1, E2, E4, E5, E6 and E7) and late genes (L1 and L2) [10]. The viral capsid moves HPV into basal squamous cells where it is extended and encoded by L1 and L2 genes. E5, E6 and E7 genes are important for integration into host DNA and uncontrolled activation of oncogenes in basal layer cells [14].

In the Republic of Moldova, the screening program is still being implemented, but the incidence, mortality and the proportion of diagnosis in advanced stages (FIGO III and IV) of cervical cancer remains a current problem with all the consequences on the lives of women aged 35-45 years [9].

Aim of the study

Due to the fact that cervical cancer in the Republic of Moldova is a serious public health problem caused by a delayed approach to its prevention, diagnosis and treatment, we aimed to: detect the factors that cause the occurrence of LSIL of the cervix; evaluate the methods of cytological diagnosis of patients with LSIL of the cervix; evaluate the techniques of immunocytochemical diagnosis of LSIL of the cervix and determine the screening algorithm of patients with LSIL of the cervix.

Materials and methods

The subject of the study included a group of 135 patients diagnosed with CIN 1 and ASC-US, hospitalized in the Oncology Institute of the Republic of Moldova during 2017-2021. A retrospective and prospective study of the hospitalized patients was performed.

Clinical observation records of patients were included, they were selected based on predetermined criteria.

As research materials we used: sociological survey data and data from clinical observation sheets, with appendices; biological substrates (vaginal secretions, cells collected from the exo and endocervix, tissue fragments taken by incisional and excisional cervical biopsy).

Descriptive statistical processing of the data obtained from the observation sheets was carried out in Microsoft Office Excel. The confidentiality of patients' personal data was respected.

Results

The study carried out on 135 patients with LSIL of the cervix confirmed both clinical and paraclinical data which are demonstrated in the tables and figures below.

Figure 1 shows the age distribution of patients with LSIL of the cervix, patients aged 17 to over 67 years were included in the research. Prevalence is observed in patients aged 17-26 years, prevailing ASC-US about 18.75%.

Figure 1. Distribution of LSIL patients by age

The HPV virus ranks first in the list of etiological factors of cervical cancer. Respectively it has been investigated based on the risk groups shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Distribution of HPV positive patients by determined HPV group.

From the above Figure we see that 18.52% of the patients were infected with intermediate risk HPV virus including types 26, 53, 73, 82. Another 31.85% of patients were infected with low risk HPV with types 6, 11, 40, 42, 43, 44, 54, 61, 62, 70, 71, 72, 81, 83, 84, 89. The remaining 49.63% detected with high risk HPV, types 16, 18, 31, 33, 35, 39, 45, 51, 52, 56, 59, 66, 68.

Table 1.

Distribution of patients with low-grade intraepithelial lesions.

Complaints	CIN 1	ASC-US
Abdominal pain	58 (16.67%)	49 (14.08%)
General weaknesses	42 (12.07%)	27 (7.76%)
Menometrorrhagia	37 (10.63%)	25 (7.18%)
Abdominal bloating	14 (4.02%)	11 (3.16%)
Leukorrhea	9 (2.59%)	17 (4.89%)
Asthenia	20 (5.75%)	16 (4.60%)
Dysfunctional metrorrhagia in menopause	5 (1.44%)	3 (0.86%)
Periodic contact discharge	7 (2.01%)	5 (1.44%)
Odorous serous discharge	2 (0.57%)	1 (0.29%)

From Table 1 we observe some data from the patients' complaints specific to the clinical picture of LSIL. About 58 patients constituting 16.67% diagnosed with CIN 1 state that they had abdominal pain and 49 patients with ASC-US i.e. 14.08%. General weakness 69 patients (19.83%), menometrorrhagia 62 patients (17.81%), abdominal bloating 25 patients (7.18%), leukorrhea 26 patients (7.48%), asthenia 36 patients (10.35%), dysfunctional metrorrhagia in menopause 8 patients (2.3%), periodic contact discharge 12 patients (3.45%), odorous serous discharge 3 patients (0.86%).

Figure 3. Distribution of patients investigated according to diagnostic methods applied.

From the data presented in Figure 3 we can see a prevalence of the ThinPrepPap test diagnostic method, about 49% of patients used this method. 18% underwent biopsy, 16% used colposcopy, 10% dilation and curettage and 7% conization of the cervix.

Discussions

LSIL is known to be a precancerous condition and squamous epithelial dysplasia of the cervix associated with HPV with increased oncogenic risk [1]. These conditions are called cervical intraepithelial neoplasia (CIN) and represent an increased risk of invasive cervical cancer [2]. Precancerous conditions are classified into LSIL and HSIL, low grade dysplasia and high grade dysplasia. And the virus, which is a risk factor, in its turn is divided into HPV-infection, koilocytosis and CIN1 belonging to LSIL and CIN2, CIN3, CIS (carcinoma in situ) belonging to HSIL. The distinction between high and low grade (HSIL and LSIL) depends on the degree of nuclear and cytoplasmic maturation of the cell [11].

The clinical picture is a poor one, because certain clinical manifestations cannot be highlighted, especially the early stages are totally asymptomatic and may become manifest after the decrease of antiviral immunity, or the disease is detected by routine examination at the gynecologist or screening. Also clinically manifestations occur when precancerous changes begin to be malignant.

Diagnosis of precancerous conditions includes: clinical examination by a specialist [6, 13]; immunocytochemical testing [3]; electron-echo investigations; cytology (Pap smear) [6]; viral genotyping by HPV-DNA testing [4, 6]; colposcopy [6, 12]; CT or MRI if a large formation has been detected [8]; biopsy, with subsequent histological investigation [12].

General conclusions

1. The most affected age group is between 17-26 years of age of which 18.75% of patients were detected with ASC-US.

2. The primary factor contributing to LSIL of the cervix is the human papilloma virus which was detected

in 49.63% of high risk patients and the remaining 50.37% had a combination of infections from those intermediate and low risk strains.

3. The most common complaints are abdominal pain (30.75%), general weakness (19.83%), menometrorrhagia (17.81%), asthenia (10.35%).

4. The most commonly used method for diagnosing low-grade intraepithelial lesions was the ThinPrepPap test, about 49% of patients used this method and 18% underwent biopsy.

Bibliography

1. Akihiro Karube, Fumiko Saito, Masato Waga, Shota Yokoyama, Katsuhiro Kanamori. Progression of cervical intraepithelial neoplasia grade 2 lesions among Japanese women harboring different genotype categories of high-risk human papillomaviruses. In: J Rural Med, April 2021, number 16(2), pages 91-97.

2. Esther van der Heijden, Alberto D Lopes, Andrew Bryant, Ruud Bekkers, Khadra Galaal. Follow-up strategies after treatment (large loop excision of the transformation zone (LLETZ)) for cervical intraepithelial neoplasia (CIN): Impact of human papillomavirus (HPV) test. In: Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews, January 2015. Available at: <https://www.cochranelibrary.com/cdsr/doi/10.1002/14651858.CD010757.pub2/full>

3. Gerard Nuovo. A broad-based approach to differentiate CIN from its mimics: The utility of in situ hybridization and immunohistochemistry. In: Ann Diagn Pathol, June 2020, number 46, pages 151515.

4. Gheoghe Peltecu. Cervical cancer. In: Romanian Society of Obstetrics and Gynaecology and Roma-

nian College of Physicians. Romanian College of Physicians Commission for Obstetrics and Gynaecology, 2019, pages 12-15.

5. Hyuna Sung, Jacques Ferlay, Rebecca L Siegel, Mathieu Laversanne, Isabelle Soerjomataram, Ahmedin Jemal, Freddie Bray. Global Cancer Statistics 2020: GLOBOCAN Estimates of Incidence and Mortality Worldwide for 36 Cancers in 185 Countries. In: *CA Cancer J Clin*, May 2021, number 71(3), pages 209-249.

6. Jana Sami, Sophie Lemoupa Makajio, Emilien Jeannot, Bruno Kenfack, Roser Viñals, Pierre Vassilakos, Patrick Petignat. Smartphone-Based Visual Inspection with Acetic Acid: An Innovative Tool to Improve Cervical Cancer Screening in Low-Resource Setting. In: *Healthcare (Basel)*, February 2022, number 10(2), page 391.

7. L M Pinatti, H M Walline, T E Carey. Human Papillomavirus Genome Integration and Head and Neck Cancer. In: *J Dent Res*, June 2018, number 97(6), pages 691-700.

8. Liu Y. The clinical research of Thinprep Cytology Test (TCT) combined with HPV-DNA detection in screening cervical cancer. In: *Cellular and molecular biology (Noisy-le-Grand, France)*, February 2017, number 63, pages 92-95.

9. Marina Golovac, Ruslan Pretula, Uliana Tabuica, Ecaterina Foca, Philip Davies. Standard of organization and functioning of the cervical screening service in the Republic of Moldova, Chisinau, 2020, pages 28-58

10. Rampias T, Sasaki C, Psyrris A. Molecular mechanisms of HPV induced carcinogenesis in head and neck. In: *Oral Oncology*, 2014, number 50, pages 356-363.

11. Roberto Dina, Dulcie Coleman, Fabrizio Corsi, Joshua Poznansky etc. Cervical uterine cytology. In: *Eurocitology*, Leonardo grant, 2015. Available at: <https://www.eurocytology.eu/>

12. Stamatios Petousis, Panagiotis Christidis, Chrysoula Margioulas-Siarkou, Nikolaos Sparangis, Apostolos Athanasiadis, Ioannis Kalogiannidis. Discrepancy between colposcopy, punch biopsy and final histology of cone specimen: a prospective study. In: *Arch Gynecol Obstet*, May 2018, number 297(5), pages 1271-1275.

13. Taylor M. Jenkins, Hadi Shojaei, Sharon J. Song, Lauren E. Schwartz. Role of Ancillary Techniques in Cervical Biopsy and Endocervical Curettage Specimens as Follow-Up to Papanicolaou Test Results Indicating a Diagnosis of Atypical Squamous Cells, Cannot Exclude High-Grade Squamous Intraepithelial Lesion, or High-Grade Squamous Intraepithelial Lesion. In: *Acta Cytol*, 2020, number 64(1-2), pages 155-165.

14. Zhou R, Wei C, Liu J. The prognostic value of p53 expression for patients with cervical cancer: a meta-analysis. In: *European Journal of Obstetrics & Gynecology and Reproductive Biology*, 2015, number 195, pages 210-213.